

Integrating Quantum-Secured Blockchain Identity Management in Open RAN for 6G Networks

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Abstract—In this paper, we propose an innovative integration of Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) and Blockchain-based Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) within the Open RAN (O-RAN) framework for 6G networks to address the critical need for enhanced security and robust identity management. We first present a general architecture that takes a multi-layered approach and is carefully designed to leverage the different capabilities of quantum security and blockchain technology. The architecture ensures seamless and secure operation across different layers of the O-RAN, focusing on the Distributed Identity Management (DIM) and Management & Orchestration layers, and explains the interactions between these layers to improve the security and operational efficiency of the network. We also investigate detailed case studies and applications that demonstrate the practicality and transformative potential of integrating QKD-secured blockchain identity management systems in real-world 6G scenarios. We also address the inherent challenges and limitations of such integration and propose viable solutions to overcome them. Finally, we provide insights into future research and implementation directions and highlight the critical role of quantum-secured blockchain systems in the evolution of telecommunication networks toward a more secure, decentralized, and user-centric paradigm.

Index Terms—quantum key distribution, open RAN, self-sovereign identity, blockchain.

I. INTRODUCTION

Europe’s digital decade framework sets the target of 80% of citizens using a digital ID solution by 2030¹. This can be achieved by giving individuals or device users more control over their data and digital identity. For this reason, an Internet of Trust must be created in order to achieve more sustainable and secure Internet infrastructures. The issue of security and trust has always been central when it comes to technology, especially new technologies potentially to be embedded in telecommunications networks. Revelations about large-scale exploitation of organizations’ infrastructure or data breaches have raised awareness in the telecom ecosystem and

increased the demand for new tools and services for greater trustworthiness among the various stakeholders [1].

In light of the above, the integration of advanced security measures into telecommunications networks, particularly through the use of Quantum Key Distribution (QKD), Post Quantum Cryptography (PQC) [2], Distributed Identity Management (DIM), and blockchain technology, is an area of growing interest in the development of evolving Open RAN (O-RAN) architectures of 6G networks. There are several studies have looked at the practical implementation of QKD (which has been commercially available since the early 2000s) in modern telecommunications infrastructures and evaluated the feasibility, scalability, and security aspects [3], [4], [5]. The use of blockchain technology to improve network security and manage digital identities has also become increasingly important over recent years [6], [7], [8], [9]. Studies such as [10] have investigated how blockchain can be used to create decentralized, transparent, and tamper-proof systems for managing identities and transactions in networks. Further research has explored the potential of blockchain for security in 5G networks (for IoT more specifically) [9], which serves as a precursor to its applicability in 6G environments. The concept of Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI), where users control their digital identities without relying on centralized authorities, has been increasingly discussed in the context of blockchain technology. The authors of [11] provide comprehensive insights into the ways in which blockchain can support SSI systems, describing the mechanisms for identity verification and the potential for enhanced user privacy and data sovereignty. Recent studies have also begun to investigate the integration of QKD and blockchain into the 6G architecture for future networks [12], [13]. The paper in [14] uses SSI in O-RAN for decentralized identity management, while the paper in [15] uses QKD together with SSI. The article in [12] discusses how quantum information technology can be used for future 6G mobile networks from a technology-driven and visionary perspective. Furthermore, the authors in [16] investigate the PQC integration within the 6G infrastructure

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¹Online: <https://bit.ly/3xTsIw5>, Available: April-2024.

and operations. However, a multi-layered security architecture in telecommunications that incorporates hybrid QKD/PQC technologies and blockchain-based SSI within O-RAN has not yet been presented to address the unique challenges of 6G networks, especially in terms of scalability, interoperability and the complexity of network management.

In this paper, we propose a novel quantum-secured communication with blockchain-based identity management systems within the O-RAN framework for 6G networks to overcome the identified challenges and improve the security, efficiency, and user-centricity of future telecommunication infrastructures. In addition, we provide a comprehensive analysis of the interactions between digital identity management and network orchestration layers, present practical applications through case studies, and address the challenges with proposed solutions that represent a fundamental approach for future secure telecommunication infrastructures.

II. GENERAL ARCHITECTURE: A MULTI-LAYERED APPROACH FOR O-RAN IN 6G NETWORKS

The overall architecture of the proposed solution, which includes a detailed multi-layered approach with QKD, PQC, blockchain-based SSI, a key management system, and service and management orchestration (including Radio Intelligence Controller (RIC) in non-real-time/real-time, and control layer is provided in Fig. 1. This architecture enables O-RAN to leverage cutting-edge technologies in PQC, blockchain, and intelligent orchestration to create a highly secure, efficient, and user-centric network with access control mechanisms employed organically. The integration of SSI ensures that identity management is both secure and decentralized, while QKD and PQC provide robust protection against eavesdropping and future quantum threats [17]. The orchestration layers manage and optimize RAN performance in real-time and non-real-time, improving network adaptability and efficiency. The details of each layer are as follows.

Layer 0 - Open RAN: It includes virtualized RAN components, which are virtualized functions of the radio access network, such as vCU (virtualized Centralised Unit) and vDU (virtualized Distributed Unit), which operate on a virtualized infrastructure and Radio Units (RUs). RUs are physical units that handle radio wave transmissions and receptions and form a direct interface to mobile devices. vCU and vDU are part of the open RAN architecture, in which the traditional base station functions are divided into centralized and distributed components. A cell site gateway serves as the primary aggregation point for traffic coming from multiple cell sites (or base stations). Aggregation routers are network devices that aggregate traffic from multiple cell site gateways before routing it to the core network. Core routers operate in the backbone of the network, handle data transmission between different sub-networks, and manage the flow of data throughout the network infrastructure.

Layer 1 - Quantum layer (QKD and PQC): This layer is responsible for the secure distribution of encryption

keys using quantum communication methods. QKD generates and distributes symmetric cryptographic keys between two communicating entities that utilize the principles of quantum mechanics without using mathematical algorithms. The QKD provides security guarantees based on the laws of quantum physics and ensures that any attempt to intercept the key distribution can be detected [18]. The QKD system consists of quantum transmitters and receivers that are responsible for the generation and distribution of encryption keys secured by quantum principles. PQC was developed to secure communication against both classical and quantum computing threats. The PQC system comprises cryptographic algorithms that are resistant to quantum attacks and ensure that encryption, data integrity, and authentication procedures remain secure even against quantum computers [19].

Layer 2 - Key Distribution and Encryption Layer:

This layer manages the lifecycle of cryptographic keys and includes key generation, distribution, storage, rotation, and revocation and ensures that the keys are handled securely throughout their lifecycle. In this layer, the key generation module uses QKD to generate secure keys and integrates PQC algorithms for additional security measures. The key distribution module manages the secure distribution of keys generated via QKD to various network nodes. The key storage module ensures that the keys are stored securely and are only accessible by authorized components. Key rotation and revocation module regularly update keys to maintain security and manage the revocation of keys when they are compromised or no longer needed. The PQC algorithm utilizes the key generated by the QKD as the master key and calculate the symmetric key via packet exchanges (i.e. Diffie-Hellman) between two entities. Finally, the encryption layer employs the symmetric key generated by these exchanges to encrypt and data traffic.

Layer 3 - Management and Control Layer: This layer includes both service and management orchestration and control layers. The Near-Real-Time RIC (RAN Intelligent Controller) component works within the O-RAN architecture to manage RAN elements in near real time (time frame in the seconds range) [20]. It uses analytics and machine learning to optimize radio resources, control traffic load and improve QoS by dynamically adapting RAN behavior to current conditions [21]. Non-Real-Time RIC operates on a longer time scale (more than one second), and focuses on broader RAN optimization strategies and long-term policy management. It gathers information from near-real-time RIC and other sources and then makes decisions about RAN management, such as software updates, configuration changes and policy updates.

Layer-4 - Identity Layer: This blockchain-based SSI system manages digital identities and enables network users and devices to control their identity data securely and without dependence on central authorities. In the O-RAN, blockchain-based SSI can manage the identities of network components

Fig. 1: Secure Communication Architecture with QKD, PQC, SSI-Blockchain in Open RAN.

and service units, improving authentication and authorization processes [14]. The blockchain underpins the SSI, providing a decentralized and tamper-proof ledger for recording transactions, identity verifications, and policy enforcement. This enhances transparency and trust in the network.

III. INTERACTIONS BETWEEN LAYERS

In 6G networks, several interactions can be activated between the proposed multi-layer O-RAN architecture. Some of the most important interactions are as follows: **(i) QKD to Key Management:** The QKD system generates keys in a secure manner and makes them available to the key management system. The key management system then manages these keys, distributes them to the corresponding network components via quantum-secure channels (i.e., via quantum communications or PQC key exchanges), ensures their secure storage and manages their life cycle. **(ii) Key Management to Blockchain-based SSI Layer:** Secure keys from the

key management system are distributed to and used by the blockchain-based SSI layer to encrypt the transactions and identity data stored on the blockchain, thus ensuring the security of all identity management processes. **(iii) Blockchain-based SSI Layer to Management and Control Layer:** Identity verifications and policy rules stored and managed by the blockchain layer can be used by both near-real-time RIC and non-near-real-time RIC to authenticate network components and make decisions related to network management and control. **(iv) Management and Control Layer to Open RAN Layer:** The Management instructions and policies decided by the RICs are forwarded to the open RAN layer, where they are implemented in the vCU, vDU and RUs to control and optimize the behavior and performance of the RAN. **(v) Inter-layer Communications:** All communication between the layers, such as control signals, management commands and identity checks, is secured with keys distributed by the key management system and encrypted with PQC algorithms

Fig. 2: Identity layer with internal and external interactions between its components and management and orchestration layer.

to protect against eavesdropping and tampering.

A. Identity and management & orchestration layers in Open RAN

Fig. 2 shows the identity layer with internal and external interactions between its components and management and orchestration layer. More specifically, it shows how the identity of an Mobile Network Operator (MNO) accessing shared O-RAN resources is verified within a network and how this relates to the management and control of a telecommunication system with virtualized network infrastructures. The yellow colored identity layer at the top left of the diagram describes a process involving various entities (holders, issuers, verifiers) and a blockchain network in which digital credentials are requested, issued, presented and verified. Details of interaction steps between issuers, holders and verifiers can be found in [14]. These are using Blockchain Network (BCN)-enabled SSI principles, where the identity of a MNOs requesting a service (e.g. for resource usages in a slice) from the management and control layer is controlled by itself and not by a central authority. The management and control layer at the top right, outlined in green, includes components such as the SMO platform, the identity manager, decision-making and the RICs (real-time and non-real-time). It includes a system for managing and orchestrating network resources and policies.

B. QKD layers in Open RAN

The secure keys provided by QKD can be used to encrypt all data stored or transmitted within the O-RAN system, and user identities can be verified using the proposed DIM framework in the identity layer. Since only the parties involved in the quantum-safe key exchange mechanism can decrypt this information, user data remains protected from conventional

and quantum attacks. In addition, secure keys generated with QKD can also be used to implement cryptographic hash functions and digital signatures. This can ensure the integrity of identity data by enabling systems and users to verify that the data has not deviated from its original state without authorization. The steps that explain how QKD works in this figure are as follows:

- (1) **Quantum State Preparation:** Alice, acting as the sender, generates a series of quantum particles, usually photons, with defined quantum properties, such as polarization or superposition. These prepared quantum states are then transmitted to Bob, the receiver, via a communication medium, e.g. fiber optic cables or free-space transmission. After receiving these quantum states, Bob measures certain properties of the particles, randomly selecting a measurement basis — e.g. the direction— of polarization - for each particle.
- (2) **Information Exchange:** Alice and Bob then openly communicate via a classical channel the measurement bases they have used for each measurement, while keeping the actual measurement results secret. They compare the bases they have chosen for each measurement. If their bases agree, they keep the corresponding measurement result as a potential component of their shared key. If, on the other hand, their bases differ, they discard that specific measurement result.
- (3) **Key Generation:** Ultimately, Alice and Bob derive a shared secret key that enables secure communication. The security of this key is guaranteed by the principles of quantum mechanics, as any attempt by an eavesdropper to intercept or measure the quantum states would be identifiable.
- (4) **Key Storage:** The Q Key AB generated by the QKD process is securely stored within the Key Distribution and Encryption Layer.

C. PQC usage in O-RAN

Symmetric Key Generation: This phase comprises four main steps: (1) The server generates a random secret key. This key will be used for subsequent encryption/decryption. Then, the server generates a Kyber key pair (server public key, server private key). Server public key will be sent to the client in the next steps while server private key is kept secret on the server. (2-3) Bidirectional Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) exchange, in which random numbers are exchanged between A and B to facilitate the generation of symmetric keys by the PQC algorithm in the 4th step. Specifically, the server uses the client's public key (received during the TLS handshake) and Kyber's encapsulation function to generate encapsulated ciphertext (encapsulated kem secret). The client uses its private key and Kyber's decapsulation function to recover the shared secret key. Both client and server use the shared secret key along with additional information from the PKI handshake (e.g., random values) through a Key Derivation Function (KDF) to derive various session keys used for encryption, decryption, and message authentication within the session. (5) Secure Data Communications: All data is then encrypted with the symmetric key derived from PQC, so that secure communication is guaranteed from now on.

IV. SERVICES, APPLICATIONS AND CASE STUDIES

QKD combined with blockchain-based SSI can bring a revolutionary approach to identity management in O-RAN architectures. There are several use cases where this combination can significantly improve the security, privacy and decentralization of identity management processes in telecommunication networks. Some example use cases are as follows:

- i. **Secure Device Onboarding and Authentication:** If a new RU, Distributed Unit (DU) or Central Unit (CU) is added to the O-RAN, its identity must be authenticated to ensure that it is legitimate and secure before it is integrated into the network. By using QKD for secure key exchange and blockchain-based SSI for decentralized identity verification, it can be ensured that the identity of each device is verified without relying on central certification authorities, increasing security against man-in-the-middle attacks and reducing the risk of credential forgery.
- ii. **Dynamic Network Slicing:** Managing the identities and access controls of network slices is crucial. With QKD and blockchain-based SSI, each network slice can securely manage its own set of identities for devices and services, ensuring that access per slice is controlled with high security and without interference. Moreover, the immutable records in the blockchain can provide a reliable audit trail of which entities have accessed each slice [22].
- iii. **Multi-Vendor Interoperability:** O-RAN enables a multi-vendor environment in which different components of the RAN are obtained from different providers [23].

In this scenario, blockchain-based SSI can enable each component from different providers to have a verifiable and immutable identity, ensuring trust and security in the integration of these components. QKD ensures that the keys exchanged between these components for secure communication cannot be intercepted or undermined.

- iv. **Secure Roaming between Operators:** In roaming scenarios, the use of blockchain-based SSI can allow users to maintain control of their identity across multiple operators, facilitating trust without relying on a single operator's PKI system. QKD can ensure that all keys exchanged during the roaming process are secure and tap-proof, maintaining confidentiality and integrity across networks.
- v. **Virtual Network Function (VNF) Life Cycle Management (LCM):** Managing the lifecycle of VNFs across different virtualization infrastructures with secure and trusted interactions between multiple stakeholders and systems may be possible with QKD and blockchain SSI. Blockchain-based SSI enables the decentralized and transparent management of VNF identities and the associated rights and supports interoperable lifecycle management. QKD secures the communication channels used to provision, manage and decommission VNFs and ensures that all operations are protected.
- vi. **Secure UE Registration:** By implementing PQC-based key generations on the network side (e.g., gNBs, Controllers), O-RAN can establish more secure communication channels between network elements. This, in turn, protects user data and signaling information as it travels through the network, ultimately benefiting and improving the UE security.

V. CHALLENGES, LIMITATIONS AND POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS

There are several challenges and limitations when integrating advanced technologies such as QKD, PQC and blockchain-based SSI systems into O-RAN for 6G networks. Although many companies such as Apple, Signal and Google have already integrated their quantum-resistant solutions into their services/products, there are several issues related to implementation challenges and technological maturity. For example, Google Chrome has started using the Kyber768 quantum-resistant key agreement algorithm for TLS 1.3 and QUIC connections to protect Chrome's TLS traffic from quantum cryptanalysis². However, this switch to PQC has brought some problems, such as the rejection of some connections that use Kyber768 after the ClientHello TLS handshake rather than switching to classical cryptography if they don't support X25519Kyber768. The implementation of hybrid systems for widespread use can be helpful as a possible solution. Another problem is the potential latency that can be introduced by the

²Online: <https://blog.chromium.org/2023/08/protecting-chrome-traffic-with-hybrid.html>, Available: April-2023.

TABLE I: Comparison of QKD with blockchain-based SSI vs. traditional identity with PKI system in Open-RANs

Characteristic	Traditional Identity with PKI	QKD with Blockchain-based SSI
Identity Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Centralized management where a trusted third party controls identity data and distribution. – Mature, widely understood and tested framework for managing digital certificates and keys that is less complex and costly to implement compared to the use of new technologies. – In closed networks or internal systems of a single operator, where the infrastructure and all participating entities are under controlled management, conventional PKI systems may be sufficient. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Allows device owners to securely control their identity data. – Enhances security (e.g. for IoT devices operating within Open RAN infrastructures or real-time security in edge services), – Reduces central points of failure, and provides a more flexible, transparent, and user/device-controlled approach to identity management
Key Distribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Key distribution relies on conventional cryptographic methods that are potentially vulnerable to quantum attacks. – Supports secure VPN setups (that require secure key distribution) by facilitating the distribution of certificates that authenticate. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – QKD ensures a secure distribution of encryption keys that is theoretically secure against any computational attack. – Secure RAN Infrastructure Communication with keys distributed in a manner that is inherently secure against interception and quantum attacks – Keys are only distributed among verified and authorized network elements.
Security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Relies on cryptographic security, which could be jeopardised by advances in quantum computing. – Natively supports the establishment of secure and encrypted communication channels using TLS/SSL protocols 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Increased security through quantum-resistant cryptographic processes and the immutability of the blockchain. – VNFs in Open RAN can be securely authenticated and lifecycle management from instantiation to decommissioning can be secured with securely managed keys distributed to these VNFs.
Trust Model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Trust depends on central authorities and the PKI infrastructure to validate identities and transactions. – Highly effective in managing and verifying digital certificates issued to vendors and their equipment in multi-vendor environments of Open RAN. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Trust is decentralized and facilitated by cryptographic verification on a blockchain. – Dynamic policies in O-RAN related to security, access, and service quality across various network components and vendors
Scalability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – High scalability (e.g. to a large number of IoT devices) managed through established PKI systems that are efficient but potentially vulnerable. – Handle the scaling of security mechanisms in scenarios (e.g. sudden increases in demand, geographic expansion or emergency network deployments). – Less computing and bandwidth resources. In developing regions, resources for deploying O-RAN with QKD or maintaining a blockchain may be limited. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Potentially limited by blockchain throughput and the current technical scalability of QKD systems. – Rapid and scalable deployment of numerous edge nodes in O-RAN with secure, verifiable identities and secure key distribution at edge.
Interoperability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Well-established interoperability standards that are widely adopted in the existing infrastructure. – Compatibility with existing systems reduces the need for major changes – Manage the cost and complexity of integrating new and old technologies and the transition to O-RAN at a manageable pace for operators. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Requires standardized protocols for integration into existing systems and cross-blockchain functionality. – Consistent and secure identity and access management and secure exchanging of keys across cross-domain communications of O-RAN.

blockchain due to the time required for consensus processes, which may not be suitable for time-critical network operations in the O-RAN. As a possible solution, blockchain technology can be expanded through more scalable architectures. Furthermore, quantum-resistant blockchain has been theoretically shown effective and feasible in recent years [24]. In terms of privacy protection, the immutability of the blockchain could conflict with data protection laws that provide for the possibility of deleting data. One possible solution is the implementation of privacy-enhancing techniques such as zero-knowledge proofs in blockchain systems, which allow sensitive data to be processed without jeopardising user privacy. Finally, the use of QKD and blockchain technologies can be resource-intensive and costly, especially in terms of initial setup and ongoing maintenance. One possible solution is the use of cloud-based services and the sharing of infrastructure between operators to reduce costs.

To summarize our proposed ideas and theoretical foundations, Table I compares QKD with Blockchain-based SSI vs. Traditional Identity with PKI system in Open-RAN. In general, QKD with blockchain-based SSI offers a high level of security and privacy, user control over identity data and resilience to future cryptographic threats, while implementation costs are currently high, the technological maturity of QKD is still emerging and the blockchain has scalability issues. On the other hand, traditional identity with PKI system is

an established technology with a proven framework and wide acceptance in the industry, while the centralized trust model is vulnerable to future quantum threats and may represent a single point of failure. Overall, we believe that QKD with blockchain-based SSI has lots of advantages to justify the costs it comes with it.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

In this paper, we have investigated a novel multi-layered architecture that integrates a hybrid QKD/PQC solution with blockchain-based SSI identity systems within an open RAN framework for 6G networks. The interactions between the identity layer, the management and orchestration layer, the key distribution and encryption layer, and the quantum networking layer within an Open RAN framework have been thoroughly analyzed in terms of network operability and security. Case studies have also been provided to study the practicality of the proposed solution in the context of Open RAN deployments. Future research could aim to extend the range and reliability of secure quantum communication (e.g. with satellite-based systems) and simulation- or emulation-based implementation of the proposed multilayer architecture to evaluate its effectiveness compared to conventional approaches.

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